

ENHANCING THE TREATMENT EFFICIENCY OF FAT-CONTAINING WASTEWATER USING ELASTIC POLYURETHANE FOAM FILTERS

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In the technological scheme of meat processing enterprises, water is used for washing products, equipment, tools, cooling machinery and technical equipment, transporting raw materials and preparing reagents. The concentration of fats and suspended solids in the wastewater of the meat industry in Ukraine and developed countries ranges from 600 to 2000 mg/l, while the chemical oxygen demand (COD) varies from 1000 to 2600 mg/l [1,2].

According to current regulations, when discharging wastewater from meat processing enterprises into the municipal sewage system, the permissible concentration of fats is 20–100 mg/l, suspended solids — up to 500 mg/l and COD — up to 1000 mg/L [1–3]. Each year, the requirements for wastewater quality become more stringent, necessitating the improvement of local treatment facilities to ensure compliance with established standards.

Under real operating conditions, such wastewater is most commonly treated using a three-stage scheme that includes mechanical, physico-chemical, and biological treatment [1,2]. Among the mechanical treatment methods, screens and grit chambers are commonly used and are installed upstream of sedimentation tanks. In grit chambers, the removal efficiency of fats and suspended solids is 10–15%, while in sedimentation tanks it reaches 30–50%. The reduction of COD and biological oxygen demand (BOD) at this stage is minimal and is mainly achieved by removing suspended solids and fats.

Combining coagulation and flotation in treating wastewater containing fats enables more advanced purification, achieving fat removal efficiencies of 93–98%, suspended solids removal of 85–96%, and COD reduction of 50–86% [3]. Commonly used

coagulants include inorganic salts such as iron and calcium chlorides, iron and aluminum sulfates, as well as other organic and inorganic coagulants.

Biological treatment and post-treatment facilities achieve the highest treatment efficiency: fat removal reaches 99–100%, suspended solids — 95–98.2%, and total BOD — 97–99.5%. The research [4] also confirms the effectiveness of combining biological treatment with membrane technologies.

A comprehensive analysis of existing data on the removal of fats and suspended solids from fat-containing wastewater using conventional methods (sedimentation, flotation, biological and chemical treatment) shows that none of these methods alone ensures full compliance with the discharge standards for municipal sewer systems [1–4]. Therefore, the aim of the research is to identify new materials and technologies for treating wastewater from meat processing enterprises before discharge into municipal sewers remains highly relevant.

In our opinion, one of the promising directions in the treatment of wastewater containing high concentrations of fats and suspended solids is using filters loaded with oleophilic synthetic materials, such as elastic polyurethane foam (EPF), expanded polystyrene, or shredded foam plastic [5]. This approach can enhance treatment efficiency and reduce the size of treatment equipment at meat processing enterprises.

The key parameters of the filtration process that determine the efficiency of treatment include the particle size of the filter media, material density, filter bed height, and filtration rate [5].

In our previous study [6], the performance of a filter loaded with elastic polyurethane foam (EPF) in cubes with edge lengths of 10, 20, 30, and 40 mm was researched. The diameter of the experimental filtration column filled with EPF granules was 100 mm, and the height was 2.5 m. The experiments were conducted under laboratory conditions using an artificially prepared solution. The height of the filter media layer ranged from 1.5 to 2.0 m, and its density was 50–70 kg/m³.

Fats and suspended solids used in the experiments were collected from the sludge of operational sedimentation tanks at meat processing enterprises in Kharkiv. The concentration of impurities in the model solution was: fats — 600–2000 mg/l, suspended solids — 600–2000 mg/l.

The optimal cube size of the EPF filter media was selected using a squeezing device consisting of rubber drums for compressing the media (Fig. 1).

According to the research results, the size of EPF granules within the range of 10–40 mm has virtually no impact on treatment efficiency or filtration duration, provided that the filter bed height is 1.5–2.0 m and the material density is 50–70 kg/m³, at a filtration rate of 5–15 m/h. A slight increase in purification efficiency was observed when using 10–20 mm granules, which was approximately 10% higher than 30–40 mm granules.

Observations of the squeezing device operation also indicated that, for reliable gripping of the material by the cylindrical drums, the grip angle α must be less than the friction angle (approximately 30°) [6]. The angle was calculated considering the drum diameter and the size of the filter media granules.

Figure 1. The design of the squeezing device:

- 1 – guiding ‘visor’; 2 – driven drums; 3 – receiving hopper; 4 – driving drum;
5 – container for collecting the regenerate; 6 – pipeline for regenerate discharge;
7 – casing; 8 – steam supply pipeline.

It was established that the minimum drum diameter ensuring reliable capture of EPF granules sized $20 \times 20 \times 20$ mm is 150 mm. Increasing the diameter to 300–450 mm allows for gripping media cubes up to 40 mm in size. Given that the optimal granule size is 20 mm, these parameters are considered technological in further analysis. The temperature in the squeezing zone must correspond to the plasticity of the retained organic matter.

The transportation of EPF filter media to the filter and its discharge using a hydraulic system through pipelines. Research has shown that the pipeline diameter should be at least five times the granule diameter. The optimal water supply intensity for efficient media transport is $19 \text{ l/m}^2 \times \text{s}$ [6].

Thus, the conducted studies have made it possible to determine the optimal EPF granule size at $20 \times 20 \times 20$ mm. It is recommended that the filter media be regenerated using a squeezing method on drum-type devices with a steel drum diameter of 150 mm and a grip angle of $28\text{--}33^\circ$. The delivery of the filtered material to the regeneration unit and back to the filter is performed hydraulically, with a water supply intensity of 19 l/cm^2 .

Further research is planned to focus on identifying additional filtration parameters that influence treatment efficiency, particularly the height of the filter bed, density of the filtering material and filtration rate.

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